

SPATIAL RENDERING OF AUDIO-TACTILE FEEDBACK FOR EXPLORATION AND OBJECT INTERACTION IN VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper an integrated system for the creation of a combined audio and tactile display is described. In order to get an illusion of physically being among virtual sounding objects, we used vibration motors attached to a belt to give tactile stimulus, and sensed the user's position and orientation with a 3D tracker. Collisions with free-to-move virtual objects is provided through semi-realistic vibration on the correct collision point with respect to the position and orientation of the user. The tactile vibration is encoded on 8 vibrotactile motors using a calculation of the gains on the motors similar to a panning law and improved to convey the perceptual illusion of proximity of the object and collision with it. We combine the tactile stimulus with a spatialization system augmented with distance cues. As a case scenario, *simpleLife*, an immersive audio-tactile installation for one participant, inspired by the concept of performance ecosystems and ecological approaches to musical interaction is shown.

1. INTRODUCTION

Realistic rendering of tactile sensation in Virtual Environments (VEs) is an active research topic with applications of interest in many research disciplines. For example, body-tactile feedback can be used to increase the users sense of presence in the virtual world. In sonic interaction design (SID) the use of haptic feedback can be used together with the sonification of motion in order to close the loop in the two coupled modalities [1]. In the area of realistic multimodal simulation in VE, the haptic shoes of Serafin and Turchet [2] provide audio-haptic integration and rendering of footsteps on different simulated surfaces.

Vibration feedback can also provide cues about orientation and help navigation in different environments when the visual cue is saturated or impaired. Tsukada and Yasumura [3] proposed a belt-type tactile navigation system that can transmit directional information to the user.

For different contexts, the haptic jacket [4], a wearable tactile display that delivers movie-specific tactile stimuli, was designed to create more emotionally immersive experiences while watching movies.

This study aims towards an integration of audio spatialization and tactile rendering for SID, using as a case scenario the context of multi-media installations. In particular, we target compositional strategies inspired by the concept of ecosystems where the interaction paradigm shifts from goal-oriented interaction towards a co-presence of participant and virtual system. The interaction relies on mutual awareness of presence and a physically informed symmetric capability of disturbing each other. The role of the composer is thus to author a process and the rules that regulate the life of this system which affect and is affected by the physical presence of the listener in a continuous feedback. More technically, we are interested in displaying in the sonic and tactile domain the collisions with virtual objects, which emit sounds and take advantage of the two modalities as spatial indicator.

2. BACKGROUND: PERCEPTUAL CUES IN THE TACTILE DOMAIN

A tactile display that not only renders the collision with virtual objects but also provides means for interaction with the VE needs to integrate both spatial and temporal cues of physical interaction with virtual sonic objects. We concentrate on how tactile illusions can provide spatial cue for the rendering of collision with virtual objects. Secondly we examine the importance of action in perception when interaction in VE is simulated.

2.1 Tactile illusions

When it comes to haptic and tactile perception, literature abounds of interesting and amusing illusions. Hayward [5] presents a taxonomy of haptic and tactile illusions and a DIY guide to easily construct devices able to provide certain tactile illusions. Following this taxonomy, we focus on the the category of mislocalization of stimulation on the skin. The cutaneous rabbit effect is one example of such a localization illusion. When vibrotactors are applied on the arm 10 cm apart, firing short pulses at discrete locations on the skin with a time delay of few tens of milliseconds,

the result is felt as a progression of pulses on the path from one location to the next rather than separate vibrations.

For our application, we want to focus on the phantom tactile illusion also known as 'funneling'. Also in this illusion vibration is provided by electronically-driven vibrotactile pulse generators. When two vibrations are applied, this time simultaneously, in certain condition of spacing the vibration is felt in between the two stimuli. In addition, modulating the relative intensity of the stimuli can be used to control the perceived position of the phantom vibration along the path between the two. This illusion is flexible because it affords both spatial control of the tactile rendering and also kinetic control, the movement of the tactile sensation.

2.2 Enaction: the concept of action in perception

In cognitive science the concept of enaction was firstly coined and elaborated by Varela, Thomson and Rosch [6]. The authors build a theory of action in perception or perceptually guided action. Among many others, an important statement of the enaction theory is that knowledge acquisition is an exploratory act of perception-action interaction in the environment involving the coordination of different sensory modalities. Moreover, the actions performed by a user play an important role in how they perceive the nature of the environment with which they are interacting.

A thorough discussion of enaction and the different takes on the concept is outside the scope of this paper. Nevertheless, we wish to point out the specific aspects of enaction theory that motivate this work towards the goal of enhancing presence and immersion in the virtual environment we intend to simulate.

In our case, the environment and the participant are here tightly coupled together through the audio-tactile modalities. Once we provide vibrotactile stimuli to the body in conjunction with an audio cue, the two modalities structure the rules governing the sensory changes produced by various motor actions, namely, the sensorimotor contingencies [7]. The sensorimotor contingencies present invariance properties that are specific to the modalities and, according to the enaction theory, prior knowledge about this contingency builds expectancies of perception. Movements are sources of information and information, when perceived, is used to regulate movements. In natural or virtual interaction, a lawful relationship exist between action and perception so that it can be learnt (enactive knowledge). Learning consists of discovering and optimizing this coupling in different contexts for different purposes.

This acquisition of skills can be broken down in several sensorimotor skills involving the different senses. In particular here we focus on the Prospective control, which is "the anticipation of future place of contact and time-to-contact based on spatio-temporal information contained in optic, acoustic, or haptic energy arrays" [8].

For instance, in visual VEs, head tracking can be used effectively to adjust the perspective of the 3D rendered environment on a flat screen or projection so that the movement of the user affects the visualization, in turn providing the illusion of a 3D world.

Specifically in our case, we can refer to audio-motor contingencies as well as tactile-motor contingencies. In analogy with the visual domain, we want to give the possibility to the user to provoke the collision and continuously perceive the result of their action (bouncing against the object, collision, audio-tactile feedback from the event, source goes away and might bounce against a wall or another object and bounce back, etc.). These potential behaviors (affordances) that are available to the participant in the environment we are creating influence the believability and the immersion in the VE. Enaction plays an important role in the perception of affordances in that they are perceived through the action-perception loop [9].

By creating a physically informed collision and contact rendering through tactile feedback both in terms of spatial (localization of the vibration) and dynamic rendering (amplitude and temporal behavior) we hope to increase the sense of immersion and enaction with the virtual environment. For the former a common spatialization rendering for the two modalities will be used. For the latter, by relying on the concept of weak sensorimotor integration, as introduced in the context of enactive interfaces for musical expression by [10], we will use an approximation of the force of the collision between objects as the driver for controlling both the sound parameters as well as the intensity of vibration of the tactile display.

3. RELATED WORKS

Since this work consists of an integration of perceptual cues in the audio and tactile modalities, we structure the reminder of this section first discussing previous work that specifically address low-resolution vibrotactile display in VEs. After that, we present compositional strategies that inform the sonic processes we wish to display in the audio domain.

3.1 Vibrotactile cues in Virtual Environments

Extensive work has been carried out in the scope of providing aid to navigation in a virtual world or additional information through the use of tactile actuators or tactors. Already in 2004, Ryu and Kim [11] investigated how to effectively provide the sense of collision using the vibrotactile display in different ways. They tested the effects of using a vibration feedback model (for simulating collision with different object materials), saltation, and simultaneous use of 3D sound toward spatial presence and perceptual realism, achieving an enhanced sense of presence, especially when combined with 3D sound. Furthermore, the use of saltation also helped the user detect and localize the point of contact more correctly. Rather than guidance, we are here interested in rendering the effect of very close proximity of a light object, small mass compared to the mass of the person, such as a particle or a fly.

Linderman et al. presented a wearable vibrotactile system for virtual contact and information display [12]. In their system, a collision-detection system gives the location of contact as output, which is taken as input to a mapping function of collision location to tactor actuation. Similarly

to the present work, the authors employed a simple configuration, such as eight factors arrayed around the torso, and showed to be effective in increasing situational awareness in a building-clearing task.

Bloomfield and Badler [13] have explored the use of vibratory actuators to provide collision cues to a user immersed in a virtual environment. In their system, a motion tracking system determines the body pose in 3D space. The intersections between factor locations and virtual object geometry are determined and result in driving the actuator accordingly.

Compared to these studies we would like the tactile stimulus to be integrated as much as possible with the audio presented. Integration is here intended temporally in the sense that the sound created by the physical interaction participant-object presents a temporal evolution, a dynamic consistent with the cutaneous cue provided by the factors. But also the localization cue present in the spatial audio rendering should be confirmed and enforced by cutaneous vibration delivered in the correct spot of the participant's skin. Our intention is not to notify the participant about the collision but rather provide the experience of it with a low-definition tactile display. For this it is important that no matter the display the contact with the object should be felt in the right spot and continuously moving along the skin with varying intensity as a brush.

Along these lines, Israr et al. [14] have proposed a scalable algorithm based on fundamental properties of human tactile perception to create continuous tactile brushes by means of any grid topologies of tactile displays. Their work makes use of both the mislocalization illusions presented in the previous section. While the implementation proved successful in the user evaluation, currently it shows an important limitation for our goal of continuous exploration and sonic and tactile interaction. The stroke needs to be pre-computed by the algorithm before being delivered to the user through the intensity and temporal controls for each actuator.

3.2 Music approaches to sonic environments

Ecosystemic approaches to music composition are well known and explored by different authors. Brown [15] provides a framework for the analysis and design of such systems. As a loose principle for the sonic domain, it "might involve generative sonic works that continue to develop and transform indefinitely, but with consistent structural and aesthetic properties". The main characteristic of this approach is to adopt a composition strategy relying on principles borrowed from evolution and ecosystem dynamics, including simulated multi-agent systems [16], showing social networks and self-organization properties [17]. These examples can show high level of complexity arising from simple behavioral rules and by employing different sonic strategies the dynamic evolution of the ecosystem becomes the composition.

With regards to this context, in the present work we wish to provide a sandbox for multimodal interaction of sonic-tactile qualities with the sonic ecosystem with the non-trivial consequence of letting the listener share the space

with such an entity. The evolution and organization of the multi-agent system is thus perceived and affected by the participant in a continuous feedback loop. The characteristics of the system are discovered by active exploration of the VE and this activity cannot be done without disturbing the agents. Compared to previous A-Life or ecosystemic approaches from other authors, the result we aim at is a timely and direct interaction participant-ecosystem.

4. REALIZATION

We implemented a system that integrates an audio and tactile display spatially rendered according to the position and orientation of the user. The system renders virtual objects moving on an horizontal plane co-located with the user at the height of her waist.

Our implementation currently works for one person at the time but it is easily scalable to multiple users provided the tracking method is capable of returning the ID of the person being tracked.

4.1 Hardware and wearable design

For the tactile apparatus, we used a circular array of 8 equally-spaced 310-101 10mm Shaftless Vibration Motor 3.4mm Button Type ¹.

The factors were glued on similarly shaped pads of Velcro. An elastic belt was prepared with a finer grid (16) of Velcro pads in order to be flexible for different experiment scenarios where higher resolution for the tactile display is desired (see Fig. 1).

The motors are connected to two Arduino Uno ² micro-controllers and driven by the PWM output of the boards. In this configuration, the intensity of the vibration is controlled by the duty cycle of the pulse wave while the frequency holds around 490Hz.

4.2 Tracking

The position of the participant is tracked using the Microsoft Kinect sensor together with the OPENNI drivers ³. In particular, we use the simpleOpenNI wrapper ⁴ for the visual programming environment Processing ⁵. More specifically, since we are interested only in the position of the torso, not the whole skeleton but only the vector center of mass is used.

The orientation tracking is accomplished with a Phidget Spatial 3/3/3 device ⁶. It incorporates a 3-axis gyroscope, a 3-axis accelerometer and a 3-axis magnetometer. With the combination of all three sensors it is possible to get an accurate estimate of the orientation of a solid body without ambiguities. In our implementation, rotations were calculated by integrating the gyroscope data, while the readings of the accelerometer and the magnetometer were used to

¹ <https://www.sparkfun.com/products/8449>

² <https://www.arduino.cc>

³ <http://openNI.org>

⁴ <https://code.google.com/p/simple-openni/>

⁵ <http://processing.org>

⁶ http://www.phidgets.com/products.php?product_id=1056

Figure 1: Elastic belt with 8 vibration motors equally spaced in a ring.

correct the estimations from integration errors and gyroscope drift. For the tracking of the torso of the user, only the yaw, or rotation around the global Z axis, was used. Fig. 2 shows the user wearing the tracker and the other electronics.

4.3 Audio Spatialization

Sound spatialization is considered crucial to the system both from a sonic environment perspective and an auditory display one. The aim of the system is to utilize both directional and distance cues to communicate information to the user about the arrangement and motion of the sonic objects at her proximity. Directional cues are created by panning the individual sound particles to a desired direction. The realization is based on the vector-base amplitude panning (VBAP) [18]. In VBAP only 2 or 3 adjacent speakers are active for a single source and the localization accuracy degrades gracefully as the listener is moving away from the center.

For the creation of distance cues there are no totally satisfactory practical solutions, especially for the impression of proximal sounds inside the loudspeaker rig. Sound-field reconstruction methods such as wavefield synthesis or higher-order ambisonics can achieve similar effects but are very demanding in terms of the number of loudspeakers needed, the complexity of the implementation and the computational cost. Instead, we opted for a more perceptual effect, by manipulating the cue of direct to reverberant sound energy for each particle. Based on the distance of

Figure 2: User wearing the belt and the rotation tracker.

the particle to the user, a mixing gain is determined that defines the portion of the particle sound presented directly to the listener and panned to its proper direction (the “dry” sound), and the portion that is reverberated and distributed to all loudspeakers (the “wet” sound). One independent reverberator is used per output channel to maximize diffuseness. When a sound is further than a reference distance to the user it is completely wet, on the reference distance the dry/wet ratio is equal and when the sound is very close to the listener it is completely dry. This effect provides a convincing sense of a distant sound outside of the reproduction rig moving closer till the boundary of the rig. Further physical distance cues that were considered are the attenuation of high-frequencies with distance and the doppler effect based on the relative speed of the user and the particle.

Proximity cues such as the ones described above can be more pronounced with use of binaural technology, which lifts the barrier of the loudspeaker rig. The reverberation manipulation is combined with a binaural panner in this case, which should accommodate head-tracking to prevent rotation of the sound scene with the user’s head. On the other hand, binaural panners can suffer from individualization effects compared to a loudspeaker system. Adaptation of the system for binaural technology, which would result in a truly portable setup, is an object for future study.

In order to accommodate a dynamic sonic environment with many particles or clusters of particles dispersed around, a “visibility” radius was also defined, after which particles were completely inaudible. In this way the participant can explore more effectively the sonic space and get stimulated

by individual objects as they enter the audible field.

4.4 Vibration feedback model

The vibration feedback from the collision of the sound particles on the body was modeled with a physical approach in mind. The relationship between physical and perceptual parameters of objects in contact have been studied [19] and different synthesis models for the sonic interactions between solid surfaces are available [20]. In the presence of a dynamic simulated environment, usually collision is handled by a physics engine and it is possible to use the collision model of the engine, or integrate a dedicated physical one for the synthesis of both sound [21] and tactile feedback. If the system incorporates measurements of contact or collision, then collision sounds or tactile signals can be synthesised from features extracted from the measured signals. Such an approach is described by Turchet et al. [22] for augmentation of footstep sounds, where the ground reaction force is estimated from the amplitude envelope of recorded footsteps captured with contact microphones.

In the present implementation we followed a simple and efficient approach based on the momentum of the particle colliding with the body. An envelope is obtained by sampling the magnitude of the speed of the object relative to the speed of the participant at the moment of the collision. This amplitude is then fed to a leaky integrator (a first-order recursive filter), with controllable decay characteristics. This simplified contact model allows control of the particle stiffness, which is perceptually associated with the hardness or stiffness of the material. The envelope applied to the motor gains is shown in Fig. 3. The contact envelope can be used to modulate the amplitude of both the sound and the motor signals. With more than one particle colliding at the same time, the individual results of the modulated amplitudes are combined with the spatialization gains and distributed to the respective motors properly.

In the absence of a real contact with objects, we have not taken a specific sound synthesis approach for a collision sound. It is left to the sound designer to decide on the synthesis approach, which can be realistic, abstract or cartoonish.

4.5 Spatialization of the tactile stimulus

For the creation of the phantom sensation between two motors, the respective amplitudes of each one should be controlled with a specific gain so that two criteria are fulfilled: a) the user can perceive a continuous sensation without “holes”, and b) the phantom sensation should produce the same perceived intensity at all positions between the motors. Various distributions have been tried out in the literature. Alles [23] indicates that a logarithmic variation of the amplitudes gives an equally intense sensation at all points. Rahal et al. [24] tested both linear and logarithmic gain distributions, with similar conclusions about the logarithmic one. Both of these studies were investigating regions on the arm. In the present system which is placed around the chest, a constant power law was followed, similar to the model presented by Israr et al. [14] for a 2-dimensional tactile display on the back of the user. For the creation of a

Figure 3: Our vibration feedback model for an object approaching and colliding with the participant.

Figure 4: Spatialization of the vibration feedback on the belt. The contribution of the individual objects are summed together and encoded in the 8 motors.

phantom sensation carrying the vibration signal S between two motors spaced at a distance D and at position d from the first motor, the signals which should be sent to each motor are:

$$S_1 = g_1 S, \quad S_2 = g_2 S, \quad (1)$$

where g_1, g_2 are the respective gains of the motors, given by the relation:

$$g_1 = \sqrt{1 - \frac{d}{D}}, \quad g_2 = \sqrt{\frac{d}{D}}. \quad (2)$$

For circular arrangements such as the present setup, we can directly replace lines with arcs to determine the above ratios for the gains, see Fig. 4. The amplitude curves given by the formulation above are shown in Fig. 5a. This curve is also close to the logarithmic curve example presented by Rahal et al. [24].

The constant power law used for the spatialization of the tactile stimuli has exactly the same objectives as the pan-

Figure 5: Amplitude gains for equal perceived intensity of phantom source in a) between two motors and b) between two loudspeakers.

ning laws of audio stereophony or the more general formulation of amplitude panning of VBAP. Both aim for a continuous sensation and a constant perceived intensity. Similarities between the phantom sensation on the skin and the spatial hearing cues have been pointed out more than 50 years ago [25]. It is expected by the authors that even though the amplitude panning curves exhibit slightly different shapes (see Fig 5b) they could also be used for spatialization of the tactile stimuli in circular or spherical grids of motors without significant degradation, but this remains to be tested properly.

5. SIMPLELIFE: A CASE STUDY

In order to test our implementation, a generative musical piece made previously by the author was modified accordingly. *simpleLife* is a short process piece for an arbitrary number of channels. The process follows the life of a self-generative ecosystem of sound particles the behavior of which emerges by the author’s definition of basic rules such as attraction, repulsion, pro-creation and life span. Each particle represents a point-source in space, free to move and rendered by means of VBAP. Starting with only two sound particles, every time they meet, they have a chance of creating an offspring particle. The life span of each sound particle is randomly set when created. In the current implementation each particle carries a sinusoid. When a particle is born its frequency is the highest and decreases as it gets older. Their aging results in an overall pitch shift along a musical scale defined by the author. The visual display of the process is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: The physics engine of *simpleLife*. The listener is represented as a red sphere in the middle, free to move in the horizontal space

Figure 7: Max/MSP patch receiving the motors gain from the spatialization engine and sending the controls to the belt via the two Arduino controller.

5.1 Realization

The physical engine and the sonic eco-system are implemented with the Processing programming environment. In this part, the gains for sound and tactile spatialization are also calculated. Those controls are then sent to a Max/MSP⁷ patch, where the sound of the individual sources is rendered. The maxuino⁸ environment was chosen for easy communication with the Arduino microprocessors through Max/MSP. Regarding the audio side, the system resembles the spatial swarm granular synthesis engine by [26]. It is not bound though specifically to granular synthesis and in this aspect it resembles the more general compositional framework for the control of sound spatialisation in computer-aided composition by Schumacher et al. [27].

A GUI is available to the user to control certain parameters of the environment and of the interaction, such as custom global forces, attraction to the participants position, and collision characteristics. On the Max/MSP side another interface shows the gain of the individual motors (Fig. 7).

5.2 Interaction

Interaction with the system was focused on specific aspects related to the audiotactile perception. Preliminary testing of the system was performed by the authors in an

⁷ <http://www.cycling74.com>

⁸ <http://www.maxuino.org>

exploratory way. More specifically, the parameters of the system were adapted in order to isolate or enhance any audiotactile cue or sensation that was deemed relevant to the objectives of the system. Such cases were: a) trying to localize unique particles or clusters in proximity and reach them, b) isolate a single particle and move around it in order to test the smoothness and the accuracy of the tactile motion, c) determine if in cases where sound localization is ambiguous the tactile sense can provide extra information to distinguish individual objects, d) focus on the transition between location cues coming from the sound only and from the sound and tactile feedback together, e) experience a multitude of surrounding particles and move within them and f) test and tune the collision with a particle and how much information it can convey, either with a static user or a static particle.

More general objectives, especially in the case of a sonic eco-system, are to enhance the presence of the user inside the environment and to provide additional feedback about its state.

6. DISCUSSION

We now proceed with a series of observation collected by the authors' themselves through the testing of the system. All these observation needs validation and extensive testing but are reported here as preliminary results for further analysis.

For what concerns the localization in interaction, (a) and (b), Exploration of the environment revealed that by setting the radius of audibility small enough, different clusters could be distinguished easier. The design proved successful in the rendering of moving objects in contact with the participant and rotating around the torso. Circular brushes are delivered using the funneling illusion combined with the tracking. This confirms that the model we implemented to be appropriate to create phantom tactile sources. With the user orientation information from the tracker, it is also possible for the participant to spin around their center and feel the continuous tactile movement due to their own movement relative to the sound source. We believe the rotation of the torso helps localizing the contact and this interaction greatly enhances the sense of immersion and presence in the virtual environment.

Considering the integration of spatial cues in the two domains, (c) and (d), we found that the tactile halo provides a solution to rendering sound sources very close to the listener. Specifically, when a particle is approaching the participant, there is an expectation of the natural continuation of the sound distance cues which is realized by the increasing amplitude of the tactile sensation.

In addition, at certain configurations a tactile sensation that feels like "swimming" can be developed, when many particles are surrounding the participant at close proximity (e). With respect to the rendering of the collision, this is particularly noticeable when both the attack and decay factors of the collision envelope are set to high values (f).

Even though different stiffness levels and various envelope profiles were considered, expressive control proved to be hard due to the limited responsiveness of the motors.

The models used had a fixed operating frequency so control of the stimulus was performed only through amplitude modulation. In future work more advanced factors will be tested that permit to feed them directly with an audio signal and hence control their vibration in an efficient and accurate way.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we have presented a practical implementation of a spatialized audio-tactile display based on low-resolution factors placed on a ring and anchored to a wearable belt. By getting tracking information from the Microsoft Kinect sensor about the location of the participant in the space and commercially available inertial sensors we provide the user with semi-realistic means to combine sonic and tactile interaction. The system is demonstrated and explored through the realization of an installation piece, in which the participant can interact with the sound environment in an embodied fashion. Preliminary results justify the viability of our approach in terms of usability and feasibility. However, further validation is needed on the perceptual effects that were experienced.

Future perceptual tests will focus on the accuracy and the limitations of the information that can be communicated to the user for the applications of interest. More specifically, contact perception will be studied further, when both sonic and tactile cues are provided to the user with and without the ability of free exploration, and the possibility of perceiving varying levels of hardness of the sound objects associated with inherent material properties. In terms of usability, a future step is to investigate applications of this augmented multimodal environment in the field of information exploration and display. For this, specific task-based tests should be evaluated. For instance, the participant will be asked to discover patterns in series of temporal data represented as spatially distributed sonic and tactile objects. We hope to find out that such multi-modal embodied interaction, spatialized and enactive, could facilitate the task as opposed to visual or audio modalities alone.

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